

KO'P O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYALARI VA GIPERGEOMETRIK CHEGARAVIY MASALALAR

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Ushbu maqolada aralash parabolik-giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun tip o'zgarish chizig'ida integral ko'rinishdagi ulash shartli chegaraviy masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Aralash tipdagi tenglama; chegaraviy masala; integral ulash sharti; integral tenglamalar usuli.

Gaussning gipergeometrik funksiyasi quyidagi qator bilan ifodalanishi mumkin¹

$$F(a, b, c; z) = F \left[\begin{matrix} a, b; \\ x \\ c; \end{matrix} \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n (b)_n z^n}{(c)_n n!} \cdot \frac{z^n}{n!}, \quad |z| < 1, (*)$$

Bu erda a, b, c, z ga bog'liq emas. Parametrlar a, b, c va z o'zgaruvchisi mumkinmurakkab qiymatlarni qabul qilib, $c \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$, va deb faraz qilinadi. $(\lambda)_v$ ifodasi Pochhammer belgisini bildiradi: $(\lambda)_0 := 1$, $(\lambda)_v := \lambda(\lambda+1)\dots(\lambda+v-1)$, $v \in N$,

gamma funksiyasi orqali $\Gamma(z)$ shaklida yozilgan $(\lambda)_v = \frac{\Gamma(\lambda+v)}{\Gamma(\lambda)}$, $v \in \{0\} \cup N$;

$N := \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ natural sonlar to'plami. Ko'p darajali qator berilgan bo'lsin

$$\sum_{|k|=0}^{\infty} A(k)x_1^{k_1}x_2^{k_2}\dots x_n^{k_n},$$

bu yerda yig'indi ko'p indeksli $k := (k_1, \dots, k_n)$ bo'yicha amalga oshiriladi. manfiy bo'lmagan butun son komponentlari $k_i \geq 0, i = \overline{1, n}$, ular uchunodatda, $|k| := k_1 + \dots + k_n$, koeffitsient $A(k)$ va o'zgaruvchilar $x_1, \dots, x_n$ mumkinmurakkab qiymatlarni qabul qiling.

Ta'rif (1) Ko'p darajali qator (*) agar quyidagi n ta munosabat bo'lsa, gipergeometrik qator hisoblanadi

$$f_r(k) = \frac{P_j(k)}{Q_r(k)},$$

Bu yerda P_j va Q_j - ko'phadli ko'phadlar, mos ravishda p_j va q_j darajali k . Q_j koeffitsienti $k_j + 1$; ga ega deb taxmin qilinadi; P_j va Q_j mavjud emas umumiy omillar, mumkin bo'lgan $k_j + 1$ ($j = \overline{1, n}$). bundan mustasno.

Ta'rif 1.1.2. $p_1, \dots, p_n, q_1, \dots, q_n$ sonlarning eng kattasi deyiladi. gipergeometrik qatorning tartibi (1.1.1).

Ta'rif (2). Agar barcha $p_1, \dots, p_n, q_1, \dots, q_n$ raqamlari bir xil bo'lsa, ya'ni $p_1 = \dots = p_n = q_1 = \dots = q_n$, keyin gipergeometrik qator (1.1.1) to'liq deyiladi. Gorn² xususan, ikkinchisining gipergeometrik qatorlarini o'rgangan. U ba'zi qatorlarga qo'shimcha ravishda dan seriyalar orqali ifodalanganligini aniqladibitta o'zgaruvchi yoki ikkita gipergeometrik qator mahsuloti orqali, ularning har biri bitta o'zgaruvchiga bog'liq bo'lib, asosan 34 ta mavjud 2-tartibdagi turli konvergent qatorlar. Ikki o'zgaruvchi bo'lsa, 14 ta to'liq seriya mavjud $p_1 = q_1 = p_2 = q_2 = 2$

$$F_1(a, b, c; d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n} (c)_n}{(d)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, |y| < 1, \quad (1)$$

$$F_2(a, b, c; d, e; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n} (b)_m (c)_n}{(d)_m (e)_n m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| + |y| < 1, \quad (2)$$

$$F_3(a, b, c; d, e; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_n (c)_m (d)_n}{(e)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, |y| < 1, \quad (3)$$

$$F_4(a, b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n} (b)_{m+n}}{(c)_m (d)_n m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad \sqrt{x} + \sqrt{y} < 1, \quad (4)$$

$$G_1(a, b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n} (b)_{n-m} (c)_{m-n}}{m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (5)$$

$$G_2(a, b, c, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_n (c)_{n-m} (d)_{m-n}}{m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (6)$$

$$H_1(a, b, c, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m-n} (b)_{m+n} (c)_n}{(d)_m m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (7)$$

$$H_2(a, b, c, d; e; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m-n} (b)_m (c)_n (d)_n}{(e)_m m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (8)$$

va 20 ta birlashgan qatorlar mavjud to‘liq qatorlar uchun chegara shakllari va ular uchun $p_1 \leq q_1 = 2$, $p_2 \leq q_2 = 2$, va p_1 va p_2 bir vaqtning o‘zida ikkitaga teng bo‘lolmaydi, masalan,

$$\Phi_1(a, b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n} (b)_m}{(c)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, \quad (9)$$

$$\Phi_2(a, b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_m}{(c)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (10)$$

$$\Phi_3(a; d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m}{(d)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (11)$$

$$\Psi_1(a, b, c, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m}{(c)_m (d)_n m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, \quad (12)$$

$$\Psi_2(a; b, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m+n}}{(b)_m (d)_n m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (13)$$

$$\Xi_1(a, b, c, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_n (c)_m}{(d)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, \quad (14)$$

$$\Xi_2(a, b, d; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_m}{(d)_{m+n} m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, \quad (15)$$

$$\Gamma_1(a, b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_m (b)_{n-m} (c)_{m-n}}{m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad |x| < 1, \quad (16)$$

$$\Gamma_2(b, c; x, y) = \sum_{m, n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(b)_{n-m} (c)_{m-n}}{m! n!} x^m y^n, \quad (17)$$

$$H_1(a,b;d;x,y) = \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m-n}(b)_{m+n}}{(d)_m m!n!} x^m y^n, |x| < 1, \quad (18)$$

$$H_2(a,b,c;d;x,y) = \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m-n}(b)_m(c)_n}{(d)_m m!n!} x^m y^n, |x| < 1, \quad (19)$$

$$H_3(a,b;d;x,y) = \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{m-n}(b)_m}{(d)_m m!n!} x^m y^n, |x| < 1, \quad (20)$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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